

POTTALI RAHASYA - A HIDDEN WISDOM AMONG RASAYOGAS**Dr. Ashwini Chandaragi*¹, Dr. Sangeeta Rao², Dr. Vikram S.³**

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ABSTRACT

Parada (mercury) is the core element of Rasashastra and plays a vital role in therapeutic efficacy. It enhances the potency of drugs within formulations and exhibits diverse therapeutic merits after undergoing pharmaceutical processes such as Murchan. Mercury-based medicines are traditionally prescribed in four major forms—Kharaliya, Kupipakwa, Parpati, and Pottali Rasayana—to achieve Rasayana (rejuvenative) effects. Among these, Pottali Rasayana is a unique preparation distinguished by its specialized manufacturing technique, compact form, and specific mode of administration. This article explores the theoretical foundations of Pottali preparation, alongside its clinical applications (Pottali Prayoga) across various pathological conditions.

KEYWORDS: Potalli, Daivee chikista, Gandhak, Swarna, Puta paka.**INTRODUCTION**

In Rasa classical texts mainly three types of Chikista are mentioned.^[1] They are Asuri, Manusi and Daivee. Rasa yogas comes under Daivee chikista because of its Rasayana property and its ability tackle chronic as well as acute condition of diseases. Khalveeya, kupipakwa, parpati and pottali they collectively know as Chaturvidha Rasayana. Among the 4 types of Rasayanas, Pottali Rasayana is unique in terms of its preparation, mode of administration, quick in action, less dose and easy for transportation.^[2]

Etymology

The word Pottali is derived from Puta Refers to – Shamshela Adhesion or give support pottali means packet or bundle.^[3]

Definition

Collected scattered Materials into a compact and comprehensive size it is the technique or processing which give compactness scatter materials. The Parada yogas in which its various ingredients are made into a compact size are known as Pottali.^[4]

HISTORICAL REVIEW OF POTTALI

- Samhita -Pottali used for Swedana purpose
- The first reference of Pottali Kalpana is found in Rasaratnakara in 12th century AD
- Gandhaka Drava Paka- of Rasaprakasha Sudhakara in 13th century
- Dolayantra with Gandhaka Drava – In 14 Century AD has mentioned Rasa Chintamani
- Kaparda poorna method Bhavaprakasha Atisara Adhikara
- Yogaratnakara in the 18th century AD-developed Pottali Paka in Gandaka Drava in an iron vessel for the first time
- Maximum number of Pottali kalpa's have been mentioned in the text of Rasayogasagara. 14 varieties of Hemagarbha pottali and 18 new pottali kalpas. 40 different pottali found in rasa grantha with mild variation in ingredients the number of pottali counts around 70.⁵

**Classification of Pottali
Based on appearances^[6]**

1. Bhasma Roopa Eg -Lokanatha Pottali

2. Puga Roopa Eg: Tamra Garbha Pottali

2. Based on ingredients^[7]

1. With parada -Ratna garbha pottali
2. With out parada -Gandhakadi pottali
1. Sagandha-Rasa pottali

2. Nirgandha -Vajra pottali

Method of Preparation

Mainly three types of preparation mentioned in the classics.

Shape of the Pottali^[8]

- Shikhara –arambhika
- Pugakara
- Karshya manascha varthika
- Shankara
- Lingakara

DOSE : ½ Tandula -2 Ratti

- Malla Garbha – 1\2 -1 Tandula^[9]
- HemaGarbha –1to 2 Ratti^[10]
- Pravala Garbha 1-3 Ratti^[11]

Shelf life: older is best

10 year from the date of manufacture according Rule 161-B of D&C act

Anupana -Adraka Swarasa, Nagavalli Swarasa, Madhu, Ghrita Rogananushara anupana can use.

Mode of administration^[12]

- Pottalis which are having **Gutikakara** should be **rubbed over a scratch stone** for desired number of rotations by applying Ghrita or Madhu and whole paste is administered orally.

- Sannipataja condition – Rub the Pottali with Ardraka rasa or Nagavalli rasa.
- Gain consciousness- Pradhamana Nasya
- **Kaparda Poorita**- whole medicine is powdered and administered according to the dosage

ANALYTICAL PARAMETERS^[13]

- 1. Organoleptic characteristics like colour, shape, odour, consistency, taste
- 2. Hardness
- 3. Disintegration time
- 4. Melting point
- 5. Loss on drying at 105°C
- 6. Ash value / acid insoluble ash
- 7. Water soluble / alcohol soluble extractives

POTTALI PRAYOGAS IN VARIOUS CONDITIONS**Table 1: In kayachikista.**

Diseases / Conditions	Pottalis
Shwasa, kasa, Rajayasma, kshya	Hema Garbha pottali, Rājamrgānka, Abhragarbha
Ama, Amla pitta, Grahani	Lokanatha pottali, Śaṅkagarbha, laghu pottali
Deepana, pachana	Vaiśvānara Pottali
Vata Roga, Shoola, udhara	Hema Garbha, Malla Garbha, Taragarbha pottali
Pandu, kamala, Halimaka Gulma	Hema Garbha, pravala Garbha, loha Garbha pottali
Prameha, pakshagata	Hema Garbha, visha Garbha, Tridhatu Garbha
Unmada, Apsmāra	Hiranya Garbha pottali
Kusta, pittaja vikara	Pravala Garbha pottali
Rasayana, vajeekarana	Rasa Garbha pottali

Table No-2: In shalya tantra.

Diseases / Conditions	Pottalis
Nadi vrana, Bhangadhara	Malla garbha, visha Garbha pottali
Arshas,pidaka	Hiranya Garbha pottali
Shola	Hema Garbha pottali
Vrana	Malla Garbha pottali
Ashmari	Ratna Garbha pottali
Mutra ghata	Loha Garbha pottali

Table No-3: In shalakya tantra.

Diseases / Conditions	Pottalis
All type of Netra roga	Loha Garbha pottali
Peenasa	Hiranya Garbha pottali
Mukha roga	Hema Garbha pottali
Danta shola	Hema Garbha pottali
Manya stambha	Rasa Garbha pottali
Vali palit	Gandhakadi pottali

Table No. 4: In streeroga and prasuti tantra.

Diseases / Conditions	Pottalis
Pradhara	Hema garbha, tridhatu Garbha
Kshya	Lokanath pottali, shanka Garbha, laghu pottali
Soma roga	Hema Garbha pottali
Piranga	Visha Garbha pottali,malla Garbha pottali
Garbhini roga	Abra Garbha pottali
Vajeekarana	Rasa Garbha pottali,mukta Garbha pottali
Shukra dosha	Tridhatu Garbha,Tara Garbha
Mooda Garbha	Ratna Garbha pottali

Table no-5: In Balaroga.

Diseases / Conditions	Pottalis
Jwara atisara	Hema garbha
Kamala,pandu	Loha garbha
Shwasa,kasa	Hema grbha
Kshaya	Lokanatha pottali
Gulma	Pravala Garbha
Bala kshya	Laghu pottali

DISCUSSION**Importance of Pottali**

- Pottalis are more convenient to handle as they are compact, small in size, have a firm and solid form, and are easy to transport.” “Preparation: Pottali is prepared by different methods such as Kaparda

Pūraṇa, Bhāvana, and Gandhaka Drava, which makes the Pottalis more potent.”

- Mode of administration: It is quick in action and required in a small dose. When Pārada is treated with Gandhaka, it becomes therapeutically efficacious. Pārada mixed with other drugs such as Svarṇa Bhasma and Sindūra enhances its properties

and exhibits synergistic action. These formulations are designed in such a way that they possess long-term preservative properties.”

Role of Bhavana^[14]

Samyoga- Performing Bhavana with Kumari Swarasa imparts Anulomana (carminand Deepana properties to the Pottali.”

Mardhana - particle size reduction caused by friction and the production of heat.”

Binding agent - gives compactness to the pottali

Gunantaraadhana-In *Tala Sindūra Pottali*, Bhāvana with *Rakta-varga Dravya* imparts colour to the pottali and enhances *Rakta Dhatu*.”

Role of Sudha Varga Dravya^[15]

Rasa: Katu, Tikta, Kshara

Veerya: Ushna, Sheeta

Doshagnata: Vata-Kaphahara

Karma: Agnideepana, Amapachana, Grahi

Sudha varga dravya mainly contain calcium carbonate, calcium oxide, and calcium silicate. They are alkaline in nature and increase gastric pH. Calcium, being the main ingredient, plays an essential role in many physiological activities beyond bone health, including blood clotting, nerve conduction, muscle contraction, enzyme regulation, and maintaining normal nutrient transport through cell membranes. These preparations are useful in conditions like Amlapitta, Kshay, and Atisara.

Additionally, they help activate inflammatory responses to combat respiratory infections.

Importance of Gandhaka^[16]

Gandhaka gives compactness to the pottali, increase the potency of Pottali, also neutralizing Parada dosha.

- When Parada and Gandhaka are combined in different proportions, their effects change:
- Samaguna -it becomes 100 times more potent than shuddha parada.
- Dwiguna-a Maharoga nashana, sarva kustahara.
- Triguna- Pushatwa prakashana, Jadya vinashana.
- Chaturaguna- Meda, Smruti vivardhana Vali palit nashana
- Pancha guna -Kshaya, kshayakarak roags nashana, santapa nashana
- Shadguna - Abhoota karyakrut, Sarva roghara

• Importance of Swarna^[17]

Swarna is used in two forms in pottali: Swarna Tanu Tantu and Swarna Bhasma.

1. Swarna tanu tantu – according to *Rasa Tarangini*, rubbing and administering Swarna Tantu exhibits Vishanashana properties. Due to its Madhura Rasa and Sheeta Veerya, it acts as Netrya, Garbhastapana, is excellent for Pitta Amaya Prashamana, Hrudhya, and Doubalya Hara.

2. Swarna bhasma

- Due to its Madhura Rasa and Snigdha, Rakta Prasadana properties, it acts on Urakshata.
- Prasadana of Hridaya and Rakta helps in the management of Hridroga.
- Owing to its Nadi Balya, Vata-vaha Dhamani Sthirakara, and Rasayana properties, it acts on Vata Vyadhi.

Importance of Arsenic^[18]

Due to its Katu-Tikta rasa, Tridosha-śamaka property, and Ushna veerya, it functions as Deepana, Pachana, and Amahara, and is effective in managing Jwara, Kasa, Shwasa, Ajeerna, Krimigna, and Kandunashini.

- It is valuable in conditions such as Phiranga, Visarpa, Kusta, Vrana, and Nadivrana.
- With its Lekhana, Rasayana, and Ojovardaka actions, and owing to its toxic effects, it exhibits activity against cancer cells.
- At the same time, it supports and nourishes normal healthy cells.

Importance of Kshetrikarana

Kshetra - Shareera

Karana –Preparing

Kshetrikarana is the purification and preparation of the body (*Kshetra* = sharīra) before administering *Rasaoushadhis* or *Rasayana* therapies. It ensures that the body is fit to accept and use the medicine to attain maximum therapeutic benefits, transforming potent medicines into rejuvenating Rasayana rather than acting as toxins.

CONCLUSION

Pottali preparations have a wide range of applications and can even be administered in emergency conditions. Mainly, pottalis act on **Agni** and nourish **Rasa, Raktadi** and other dhatus. These preparations are highly potent; however, very few are available in the market, and only a limited number of vaidyas use them in their treatments. To increase awareness of these formulations, more research is required for analytical and clinical evaluation of Pottali Kalpanas.

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